

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

CNN3 (Calponin 3)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	1266 / Q15417
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is a close neighbor of targets within a LFQ proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 4) contains several novel AD targets, including MSN and CD44 (1).

TREAT-AD Overall Score: 3.49 (rank #1934)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Overall Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Overall Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being

evidence of the strongest association with AD. The Center has also ranked the recency of a target's association with AD in published literature. The Literature Recency Score is on a scale of 0 to 2, with 2 being all papers linking a target and AD have been published in the most recent 5 year period. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v33.

The TREAT-AD Overall score for this target is 3.49 out of 5 (rank #1934). The individual score components include 1.51 of 3 for genetics, and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics. The literature recency score is 1.26 out of 2. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of CNN3, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. The biological domain characterization of the source module (Module 4) indicates that the proteins in this module are enriched for terms annotated to the Structural Stabilization, Lipid Metabolism, and Epigenetic domains. The most significantly enriched terms from this module are “focal adhesion”, “cadherin binding”, and “membrane raft”. CNN3 is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Structural Stabilization and Synapse biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Allen Brain Institute. The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins, points indicating the expression of the target in specific sub-types within each broad class including a label for the highest expressing cell type for each broad class. These data indicate that CNN3 expression is strongest in astrocytes in healthy adult brains, but it is also expressed in neurons, oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC), as well as pericytes and endothelial cells.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Calponin-3 (CNN3) is a cytoskeletal associated factor that binds and regulates actin mediated transport (2). Despite both genetic and genomic linkage with AD, as discussed above, it's potential role in AD is unknown. The role of CNN3 in synaptic formation in development (see below) suggests a role in synaptic stabilisation and transport regulation—consistent with the mapping of CNN3 to the Structural Stabilisation and Synapse biological domains. The CNN3 project is focused upon the development of key resources to study its role in

AD pathophysiology bundled in a target enabling package (TEP). Purified protein and validated antibodies, along with informatics resources, are the core components of the CNN3 TEP.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Calponin-3 (CNN3) binds to actin filaments, calmodulin and tropomyosin, and CNN3 interaction with actin can inhibit the ATPase function of actinomyosin, consequently regulating cytoskeletal transport (2). The N-terminal portion of CNN3 contains the calponin homology (CH) domain involved in actin filament binding followed by 3 Calponin-like domains for 26 aa each, leading to the disordered region at the C-terminus. There are several isoforms of CNN3 ranging from 283 aa to 329 aa due to variation in splicing, predominantly affecting the N-terminal portion of the protein, prior to the CH domain. Little is known about CNN3 in neuronal function, but evidence suggests that it directs neural tube closure and proper embryonic brain development, as mutant animals demonstrate profound malformation of the rostral neural tube with closure deficits and neural stem cell over-proliferation (3). There is indirect evidence that CNN3 may play a role in synaptic function, as mutants for syntaxin binding protein 1 (STXBP1), a critical protein involved in synapse formation, demonstrates altered expression levels of CNN3. The link to Alzheimer's disease (AD), in addition to that discussed in the bioinformatics section, comes from changes in mRNA expression levels in the temporal cortex and altered CNN3 protein levels in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DFPLC) between AD cases and controls (Agora).

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for CNN3. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for CNN3 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[CNN3 antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

CNN3A-c007: Near full length protein (G11-Y329) containing an N-terminal His6-Sumo1-Sumo cleavage site tag. This protein will be useful for activity assays.

Fig. 1. SEC trace (left) of CNN3A-c007 with peak fractions (denoted by star on trace) run on an SDS-PAGE gel (right).

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of CNN3 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Construct Details

Construct ID	CNN3A-c007
Parental vector	pSUMO-LIC
Tag	N-terminal His6-SUMO1-SUMO cleavage site
Protein mass (with tag)	41589.2 Da
Protein mass (with tag removed)	29029.2 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	28880
Protein sequence (with tag)	MCSSHHHHHSGSGSDQEAKPSTEDLGDKKEGEYIKLVIGQDSSEIHFKVKMTTHLK KLKESYQQRQGVPMNSLRFLFEGQRIADNHTPKELGMEEDVIEVYQEQTGGLSAEVK NKIASKYDHQAEEDLRNWIEEVTGMSIGPNFQLGLKDGIIICELINKLQPGSVKKNV NWPQLENIGNFIKAIQAYGMKPHDIFEANDLFENGNMTQVQTTLVALAGLAKTKGFHT TIDIGVKYAEKQTRRFDEGKLKAGQSVIGLQMGTKNCASQAGMTAYGTRRHLYDPKMQ TDKPFDQTTISLQMGTKNGASQAGMLAPGTRRDIYDQKLTLPVDNSTISLQMGTKNV ASQKGM SVYGLGRQVYDPKYCA
Protein sequence (after tag removal)	GLSAEVKNKIASKYDHQAEEDLRNWIEEVTGMSIGPNFQLGLKDGIIICELINKLQPGSV KKNVNESSLNWPQLENIGNFIKAIQAYGMKPHDIFEANDLFENGNMTQVQTTLVALAGL AKTKGFHTTIDIGVKYAEKQTRRFDEGKLKAGQSVIGLQMGTKNCASQAGMTAYGTRR HLYDPKMQTDKPFDQTTISLQMGTKNGASQAGMLAPGTRRDIYDQKLTLPVDNSTIS LQMGTKNVASQKGM SVYGLGRQVYDPKYCA

Expression and Purification Protocol

Expression host	<i>E. coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 μ g/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 μ g/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 μ g/ml) and cm (34 μ g/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with

	vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.6 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 100 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 20 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 10 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.
Protein Yield	7 mg/L of culture

References

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